

BIODIVERSITY INDEX OF LEECHES OF RIVERS IN THE FERGHANA VALLEY

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Abstract: *In the article, the biodiversity of leeches distributed in the rivers of the Fergana Valley was analyzed using the Shannon index. In the results, it was found that the average indicator is in the Kara Darya, Syr Darya, Ak Bura rivers, and the low indicator is in the Sokh, Govasay, Kosonsay, Isfayramsay, Maylisay rivers.*

Keywords: *anthropogenic factors, biodiversity, Ferghana Valley, leech, Shannon index.*

Natural and artificial water bodies in this area are important in determining the current state of biodiversity of Ferghana Valley leeches. The impact of lotic water bodies on the increase or decrease of biodiversity indicators is large, due to the constant movement of water. Especially, the tributaries of long rivers occupy an important place in the distribution of species. However, it is necessary to identify the types of leeches distributed in them, to study the population status, and to analyze the indicators of biodiversity (Solijonov, Izzatullaev, 2021; Solijonov, 2023).

In the research, we analyzed the species composition of leeches in the springs of the Fergana Valley, and the indicators of biodiversity in the springs. Shannon's index method was used in the analysis of biodiversity indicators of leeches. Based on the following formula:

$$H' = - \sum_{i=1}^s p_i \ln(p_i)$$

In the Shannon index, p is the proportion (n/N) of individuals of one particular species found (n) divided by the total number of individuals found (N), \ln is the natural log, Σ is the sum of the calculations, and s is the number of species. Levels of biodiversity indicators according to the Shannon index (H'): $H' < 1.5$ – low; $1.5 < H' < 2.5$ – average; $H' > 2.5$ – characterized by high values (Shannon, 1948).

In the research, in the analysis of biodiversity indicators of river leeches, special attention was paid to the orographic features of the surrounding mountain ranges, geographical location, hydrographic regime, and biodiversity indicators were analyzed (Table 1).

Table 1

Species composition of leeches distributed in the rivers of the Ferghana Valley

№	Name of rivers	Name and number of species (ind./m ²)											
		<i>Alboglossiphonia hyalina</i>	<i>Alboglossiphonia lata</i>	<i>Helobdella stagnalis</i>	<i>Piscicola geometra</i>	<i>Hirudo medicinalis</i>	<i>Hirudo verbana</i>	<i>Hirudo orientalis</i>	<i>Limnatis paluda</i>	<i>Haemopsis sanguisuga</i>	<i>Erpobdella octoculata</i>	<i>Erpobdella nigricollis</i>	Total number of species

1.	Kara Darya	20	16	42	10	2	3	4	2	23	31	29	11
2.	Maylisay	2	-	32	-	-	-	-	2	12	10	8	6
3.	Ak Bura	33	20	65	6	-	5	1	-	30	21	16	9
4.	Aravonsay	12	3	24	-	-	-	-	-	18	22	12	6
5.	Naryn	14	-	26	8	-	-	-	-	16	28	22	6
6.	Syr Darya	16	10	30	13	1	1	-	6	20	22	18	9
7.	Podshootasay	18	-	28	2	-	-	-	8	20	36	34	7
8.	Kosonsay	-	-	20	3	-	-	-	1	18	14	12	6
9.	Govasay	-	-	20	-	-	-	-	2	18	23	21	5
10.	Chodak	-	-	18	-	-	-	-	3	16	20	19	5
11.	Sokh	-	-	22	4	-	-	-	2	22	28	32	6
12.	Isfayramsay	10	-	23	2	-	-	-	-	31	22	18	6
13.	Shohimardansay	-	-	13	2	-	-	-	-	8	6	5	5

The results show that ($1.5 < H' < 2.5$) average index: Kara Darya-2.06; Syr Darya-1.8; Ak Bura-1.58; ($H' < 1.5$) low index: Naryn-1.22; Aravonsay-1.13; Shohimardansay-1.09; Podshootasay-1.05; Sokh-1.0; Govasay-0.95; Kosonsay-0.95; Isfayramsay-0.94; Maylisay - 0.68 was found (Solijonov, Izzatullaev, 2021; Solijonov, 2023). It was found that there are Isfayramsay, Govasay, Kosonsay and Maylisay rivers whose biodiversity index H' has not even reached 1.0 value (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Analysis of biodiversity index of leeches in rivers of Ferghana Valley (H').

In conclusion, it can be said that the biodiversity of leeches is affected by negative anthropogenic factors. Factors such as chemical contamination of habitats, extraction from nature by poachers are considered to be factors.

References:

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